

eTable 1. Main socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of healthy controls and FTLD patients classified by clinical presentation and genotype. Individual features of genetic FTLD patients with uncommon or double mutations are reported in **eTable 4**.

	HC	sMND	C9-MND	SOD1	TARDBP	sFTD	C9-FTD	GRN	p
Number	52	45	22	7	10	16	11	8	-
Diagnosis	-	37 ALS, 3 PLS, 5 PMA	18 ALS, 1 PLS, 3 PMA	6 ALS, 1 PLS	6 ALS, 1 PLS, 3 PMA	12 bvFTD, 2 nfvPPA, 2 svPPA	5 bvFTD, 5bvFTD/ALS, 1 svPPA	5 bvFTD, 3 nfvPPA	-
Sex (M/F)	26/26	23/22	12/10	2/5	5/5	9/7	6/5	4/4	0.973
Family history (+/-)	0/52	3/42	10/12 ^{a,b}	1/6	4/6 ^a	2/14	7/4 ^{a,c}	4/4	0.001
Education (years)	12.75 ± 3.70 [5 – 20]	12.07 ± 4.10 [5 – 24]	11.05 ± 3.47 [5 – 20]	11 ± 2.60	9.67 ± 2.89 [8 – 13]	10.36 ± 3.81 [5 – 17]	12.10 ± 4.60 [5 – 21]	8.83 ± 3.43 [5 – 13]	0.180
Age at MRI (years)	59.2 ± 6.6 [44.7 – 72.7]	58 ± 9.7 [36 – 71]	55.8 ± 9.2 [42.7 – 71.7]	55 ± 8.2 [39.8 – 62.9]	61.4 ± 6.6 [48.3 – 71]	61.4 ± 5.7 [46 – 71]	60.6 ± 3.9 [54.9 – 67.2]	62.1 ± 4.1 [53.7 – 65.3]	0.161
Disease duration (months)	-	29.6 ± 42.9 [4 – 277]	19.8 ± 21.9 [4 – 122]	61.1 ± 30.9 [7 – 93]	17.7 ± 19.4 [5 – 67]	30 ± 10.4 [22 – 48]	31.9 ± 39.6 [9 – 112]	30 ± 8.5 [24 – 36]	0.187
CDR	-	-	-	-	-	1.23 ± 0.97 [0 – 3]	0.67 ± 0.29 [0.5 – 1.00]	1.67 ± 1.03 [0 – 3]	0.340
CDR-FTLD	-	-	-	-	-	10.20 ± 6.70 [1 – 23]	5.50 ± 4.24 [2.5 – 8.5] (2)	7.83 ± 7.91 [0.5 – 20.00]	0.556
CDR-sb	-	-	-	-	-	7.53 ± 5.30 [1.00 – 17.00]	5.33 ± 2.75 [2.50 – 8.00]	7.83 ± 5.35 [1.00 – 15.00]	0.472
ALSFRS-r [0-48]	-	37.36 ± 6.2 [23 – 47]	37.1 ± 6.6 [25 – 46]	40.8 ± 6.7 [28 – 46]	33.5 ± 9 [20 – 44]	-	35.2 ± 5.6 [26 – 41]*	-	0.276
MRC sum score	-	97.08 ± 20.63 [34 – 120]	95.80 ± 23.80 [41 – 121]	109.25 ± 9.39 [97 – 118]	84.83 ± 18.75 [50 – 103]	-	90.40 ± 12.58 [78 – 110]*	-	0.421
Disease progression rate	-	0.64 ± 0.60 [0.07 – 2.40]	0.70 ± 0.39 [0.07 – 1.3]	0.18 ± 0.13 [0.02 – 0.30]	1.80 ± 1.23 ^{b,c,d} [0.18 – 4.00]	-	1.18 ± 0.60 [0.75 – 2.20]*	-	< 0.001
Onset bulb/limb/ bulb+limb	-	8/33/1	2/20/0	0/7/0	2/8/0	-	2/3/0*	-	-

Values are reported as means ± standard deviations [range]. P values refer to ANOVA models, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. * = bvFTD/ALS cases. Abbreviations: HC= healthy controls; sMND= sporadic motor neuron disease; sFTD= sporadic frontotemporal dementia; C9-MND= motor neuron disease with *C9orf72* mutation; C9-FTD= frontotemporal dementia with *C9orf72* mutation; SOD1= motor neuron disease due to *SOD1* mutation; TDP43= motor neuron disease due to

TARDBP mutation; GRN= frontotemporal dementia due to *GRN* mutation. Symbols: - = not applicable; a= statistically significant difference with HC; b= statistically significant difference with sMND; c= statistically significant difference with C9-MND; d= statistically significant difference with SOD1; e= statistically significant difference with sFTD.

eTable 2. Neuropsychological features of healthy controls and FTLN patients classified by clinical presentation and genetic status.

	HC	sMND	gMND	sFTD	gFTD
Global cognition	52	45	44	16	22
MMSE*	0.98 ± 0.03 [0.90-1]	0.97 ± 0.03 ^{b,c} [0.90-1]	0.96 ± 0.05 ^{b,c} [0.71-1]	0.77 ± 0.20 ^a [0.20-0.93]	0.78 ± 0.20 ^a [0.33-0.97]
Memory					
Digit span forward	6.23 ± 1.09 [4-9]	5.52 ± 0.94 [4-7]	5.41 ± 0.87 [3-7]	4.89 ± 1.62 [2-7]	4.29 ± 1.36 ^a [0-6]
RAVLT delayed	9.94 ± 2.84 [3-15]	10.11 ± 3.42 ^{b,c} [1-15]	8.06 ± 3.17 ^{b,c} [3-14]	2.56 ± 2.70 ^a [0-7]	4.14 ± 2.91 ^a [0-9]
RAVLT recognition	14.29 ± 0.86 [14-15]	14.35 ± 0.78 ^{b,c} [13-15]	14.15 ± 1.03 ^{b,c} [12-15]	9.29 ± 4.92 ^a [0-15]	11.30 ± 4.11 ^a [3-15]
Executive functions					
CPM	31.50 ± 3.09 [22-36]	29.12 ± 5.28 ^b [16-36]	29.38 ± 4.88 ^b [16-35]	20.00 ± 9.85 ^a [3-32]	23.13 ± 8.41 ^a [7-35]
Digit span backward	4.85 ± 1.23 [3-8]	4.54 ± 1.42 [2-9]	4.25 ± 1.41 [0-8]	3.00 ± 1.41 [0-4]	3.21 ± 1.58 [0-6]
Visuospatial abilities					
Rey Figure copy	31.38 ± 2.67 [28-36]	20.08 ± 9.16 [10-33]	-	28.50 ± 7.66 [14.5-36]	14.88 ± 10.09 ^a [0-25.5]
Language					
BADA (noun)	29.88 ± 0.35 [29-30]	29.48 ± 0.95 [27-30]	29.08 ± 1.09 [27-30]	-	27.80 ± 2.59 [25-30]
BADA (action)	27.88 ± 0.35 [27-28]	27.43 ± 0.79 ^c [26-28]	25.93 ± 2.51 ^c [18-28]	-	22.80 ± 3.70 ^a [18-27]
Token test	33.63 ± 2.03 [30-36]	29.61 ± 2.58 [27-33.5]	-	24.28 ± 10.31 ^a [7-36]	22.00 ± 14.14 [12-32]
Fluency					
Phonemic Fluency	37.31 ± 8.40 [18-55]	32.34 ± 10.72 ^{b,c} [16-65]	28.40 ± 9.69 ^{a,c} [10-55]	17.89 ± 10.43 ^a [6-30]	10.13 ± 5.60 ^a [0-22]
Index PF**	5.00 ± 1.92 [2.60-12.05]	5.57 ± 2.29 ^c [1.90-10.82]	6.75 ± 2.50 ^c [2.72-12.14]	-	-
Semantic Fluency	47.47 ± 9.45 [28-70]	40.86 ± 7.89 ^{a,b,c} [27-54]	39.09 ± 8.39 ^{a,b,c} [19-53]	19.22 ± 6.46 ^a [10-28]	21.71 ± 9.04 ^a [1-33]
Index SF**	3.71 ± 0.94 [2.49-6.97]	4.10 ± 1.22 [2.20-8.04]	4.92 ± 1.64 [3.00-8.70]	-	-
Mood & Behavior					
BDI	6.80 ± 6.10 [0-21]	10.82 ± 3.63 [6-20]	6.57 ± 3.69 [1-13]	-	-
FBI total score	-	1.95 ± 1.83 ^{b,c} [0-6]	2.82 ± 3.126 ^{b,c} [0-13]	28.00 ± 11.6 [15-45]	17.33 ± 13.09 [0-35]
ALS-FTD-Q	-	6.00 ± 5.01 ^c [2-17]	11.11 ± 11.20 [0-43]	-	30.50 ± 4.44 [26-36]
Cognitive diagnosis					
MND- cu/ci/bi/cbi/NA	-	21/1/6/2/15	19/3/4/3/15	-	-

Values are numbers or means $\pm$ standard deviations [range]. P values refer to univariate GLM analysis, followed by Bonferroni t-test for multiple comparisons corrected for age, sex and education. Comparisons among MND patients were also corrected for ALSFRS-r. *= Ratio between the number of correct items and the maximum number of administered items; **= Verbal fluency indices were obtained as following: time for generation condition - time for control condition (reading or writing generated words)/total number of items generated. Abbreviations: ALS= Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; ALS-FTD-Q= ALS-FTD questionnaire; BADA= Battery for aphasic deficit analysis; BDI= Beck Depression Inventory; FTD= frontotemporal dementia; CDR= Clinical dementia rating scale; CET= Cognitive estimation test; CPM= Colored progressive matrices; CST= Card sorting tests; FBI= Frontal Behavioral Inventory; HDRS= Hamilton Depression Rating Scale; HC= Healthy controls; MMSE= Mini-Mental state examination; MNDcu= motor neuron disease cognitively unimpaired; MNDci= MND with cognitive impairment; MNDbi= MND with behavioral impairment; MNDcbi= MND with cognitive and behavioral impairment; NA= not available; PF= Phonemic fluency; PLS= Primary lateral sclerosis; RAVLT= Rey auditory verbal learning test; SB= Sum of boxes; SF= Semantic fluency; TMT= Trail making test.

-= not applicable.

a= statistically significant difference with HC.

b= statistically significant difference with sFTD.

c= statistically significant difference with gFTD.

eTable 3. Neuropsychological features of healthy controls and FTLN patients classified by clinical presentation and genotype. Individual features of genetic FTLN patients with uncommon or double mutations are reported in **Table e-4**.

	HC	sMND	C9-MND	SOD1	TARDBP	sFTD	C9-FTD	GRN
Global cognition	52	45	22	7	10	16	11	8
MMSE*	0.98 ± 0.03 [0.90-1]	0.97 ± 0.03 ^{b,d} [0.90-1]	0.96 ± 0.03 ^{b,d} [0.90-1]	0.98 ± 0.02 ^{b,d} [0.97-1]	0.95 ± 0.09 ^{b,d} [0.71-1]	0.77 ± 0.20 ^a [0.20-0.93]	0.88 ± 0.09 ^d [0.63-0.97]	0.65 ± 0.20 ^a [0.33-0.87]
Memory								
Digit span forward	6.23 ± 1.09 [4-9]	5.52 ± 0.94 [4-7]	5.60 ± 0.63 [4-6]	5.00 ± 0.71 [4-6]	5.44 ± 1.24 [3-7]	4.89 ± 1.62 [2-7]	4.56 ± 0.92 [3-6]	3.60 ± 2.19 [0-6]
RAVLT delayed	9.94 ± 2.84 [3-15]	10.11 ± 3.42 ^{b,d} [1-15]	8.60 ± 3.25 ^b [4-14]	10.25 ± 3.30 [6-14]	7.22 ± 2.64 [4-13]	2.56 ± 2.70 ^a [0-7]	6.00 ± 1.85 [4-9]	1.25 ± 1.50 ^a [0-3]
RAVLT recognition	14.29 ± 0.86 [14-15]	14.35 ± 0.78 ^{b,d} [13-15]	14.15 ± 1.07 ^{b,d} [12-15]	14.67 ± 0.58 ^{b,d} [14-15]	14.22 ± 0.97 ^{b,d} [13-15]	9.29 ± 4.92# [0-15]	13.50 ± 2.35 ^{b,d} [9-15]	6.33 ± 3.06# [3-9]
Executive functions								
CPM	31.50 ± 3.09 [22-36]	29.12 ± 5.28 ^d [16-36]	29.36 ± 4.94 [17-35]	30.00 ± 3.67 [24-33]	28.29 ± 6.32 [16-34]	20.00 ± 9.85 ^a [3-32]	26.00 ± 6.48 [19-35]	18.00 ± 9.35 ^a [7-28]
Digit span backward	4.85 ± 1.23 [3-8]	4.54 ± 1.42 [2-9]	4.50 ± 1.63 [0-8]	3.75 ± 0.50 [3-4]	4.33 ± 1.23 [3-6]	3.00 ± 1.41 [0-4]	3.56 ± 1.59 [0-6]	2.00 ± 1.73 [0-3]
Visuospatial abilities								
Rey Figure copy	31.38 ± 2.67 [28-36]	20.08 ± 9.16 [10-33]	-	-	-	28.50 ± 7.66 [14.5-36]	23.88 ± 2.30 [22.25-25.50]	13.83 ± 7.65 [8.00-22.5]
Language								
BADA (noun)	29.88 ± 0.35 [29-30]	29.48 ± 0.95 [27-30]	29.00 ± 1.11 [27-30]	29.67 ± 0.58 [29-30]	29.00 ± 1.41 [27-30]	-	27.80 ± 2.59 [25-30]	-
BADA (action)	27.88 ± 0.35 [27-28]	27.43 ± 0.79 ^c [26-28]	26.29 ± 2.16 [22-28]	27.00 ± 1.73 [25-28]	25.86 ± 1.86 [23-28]	-	22.80 ± 3.70 ^a [18-27]	-
Token test	33.63 ± 2.03 [30-36]	29.61 ± 2.58 [27-33.5]	-	-	-	24.28 ± 10.31 ^a [7-36]	-	32.00 ± 0.00 [32-32]
Fluency								
Phonemic Fluency	37.31 ± 8.40 [18-55]	32.34 ± 10.72 ^{b,c,d} [16-65]	27.35 ± 8.51 ^c [10-45]	31.83 ± 11.27 [15-44]	29.89 ± 11.10 ^c [19-55]	17.89 ± 10.43 ^a [6-30]	12.10 ± 5.72 ^a [4-22]	6.50 ± 4.66 ^a [0-11]
Index PF**	5.00 ± 1.92 [2.60-12.05]	5.57 ± 2.29 ^c [1.90-10.82]	6.76 ± 1.85 ^c [3.27-9.19]	6.25 ± 3.94 ^c [4.00-12.14]	6.23 ± 2.35 ^c [2.72-9.43]	-	-	-

Semantic Fluency	47.47 ± 9.45 [28-70]	40.86 ± 7.89 ^{b,c,d} [27-54]	38.88 ± 7.27 ^b [26-53]	45.17 ± 7.25 ^{b,c,d} [35-53]	37.67 ± 10.22 ^{b,d} [19-50]	19.22 ± 6.46 ^a [10-28]	26.70 ± 4.47 ^a [18-33]	16.20 ± 8.59 ^a [7-28]
Index SF**	3.71 ± 0.94 [2.49- 6.97]	4.10 ± 1.22 [2.20- 8.04]	5.13 ± 1.65 [3.10- 7.89]	3.84 ± 0.51 [3.13- 4.36]	4.71 ± 1.62 [3.00- 8.08]	-	-	-
Mood & Behavior								
BDI	6.80 ± 6.10 [0-21]	10.82 ± 3.63 [6-20]	7.00 ± 5.16 [1-13]	6.00 ± 6.00 [3-12]	6.00 ± 3.40 [3-7]	-	-	-
FBI total	-	1.95 ± 1.83 ^{b,c,d} [0-6]	2-64 ± 2.46 ^b [0-7]	-	3.71 ± 4.50 ^b [0-13]	28.00 ± 11.6 [15-45]	16.33 ± 15.23 [0-35]	25.00 ± 2.40 [22-27]
ALS-FTD-Q	-	6.00 ± 5.01 [2-17]	13.44 ± 13.69 [0-43]	1.00 ± 0.00 [1-1]	9.83 ± 10.07 [1-28]	-	30.50 ± 4.44 [26-36]	-

Values are numbers or means ± standard deviations [range]. P values refer to univariate GLM analysis, followed by Bonferroni t-test for multiple comparisons corrected for age, sex and education. Comparisons among MND patients were also corrected for ALSFRS-r. *= Ratio between the number of correct items and the maximum number of administered items; **= Verbal fluency indices were obtained as following: time for generation condition - time for control condition (reading or writing generated words)/total number of items generated. Abbreviations: ALS= Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; ALS-FTD-Q= ALS-FTD questionnaire; BADA= Battery for aphasic deficit analysis; BDI= Beck Depression Inventory; FTD= frontotemporal dementia; CDR= Clinical dementia rating scale; CET= Cognitive estimation test; CPM= Colored progressive matrices; CST= Card sorting tests; FBI= Frontal Behavioral Inventory; HDRS= Hamilton Depression Rating Scale; HC= Healthy controls; MMSE= Mini-Mental state examination; PF= Phonemic fluency; PLS= Primary lateral sclerosis; RAVLT= Rey auditory verbal learning test; SB= Sum of boxes; SF= Semantic fluency; TMT= Trail making test.

-= not applicable

a= statistically significant difference with HC

b= statistically significant difference with sFTD

c= statistically significant difference with C9-FTD

d =statistically significant difference with GRN

eTable 4. Main sociodemographic, clinical and neuropsychological features of FTL D patients affected by uncommon or double mutations.

	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 3	Subject 4	Subject 5	Subject 6	Subject 7	Subject 8
Mutation	TBK1	TBK1	FUS	FUS	TREM2	MAPT	C9 + TDP43	C9 + GRN
Diagnosis	ALS	ALS	ALS	ALS	bvFTD	Right-SD	ALS	bvFTD
Sex (M/F)	M	M	F	M	F	F	F	M
Education (years)	-	8	13	-	13	-	-	13
Age at MRI (years)	75	67	31	74	49	53	47	60
Disease duration (months)	14	22	10	8	24	-	29	12
CDR	-	-	-	-	-	0.5	-	0.5
CDR-sb	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	2.5
ALSFRS-r [0-48]	-	39	36	35	-	-	-	-
MRC sum score	-	108	98	78	-	-	-	-
Disease progression rate	-	0.41	1.2	1.63	-	-	-	-
Onset bulb/limb	limb	limb	limb	limb	-	-	limb	-
Global cognition								
MMSE*	0.93	1.00	-	1.00	0.40	-	1.00	0.90
FAB	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
Memory								
Digit span forward	6	-	-	5	4	-	4	5
RAVLT delayed	3	-	-	5	0	-	7	5
RAVLT recognition	12	-	-	-	13	-	14	-
Corsi block-tapping	5	-	-	-	2	-	5	-
Executive functions								
CPM	34	-	-	26	9	-	33	29
Digit span backward	5	-	-	3	3	-	2	4

CST, perseverations**	-	-	-	-	0.26	-	0.14	0.45
Visuospatial abilities								
Rey Figure copy	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-
Language								
BADA (noun)	-	-	-	29	-	-	29	-
BADA (action)	18	-	-	24	-	-	28	-
Token test	-	-	-	-	12	-	-	-
Fluency								
Phonemic Fluency	-	16	-	18	6	-	35	9
Index PF***	-	10.4	-	11.8	-	-	4.6	-
Semantic Fluency	-	31	-	28	1	-	38	20
Index SF***	-	5.29	-	8.70	-	-	4.08	-
Mood & Behavior								
BDI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
FBI total	0	-	-	3	-	-	4	8
ALS-FTD-Q	3	11	-	-	-	-	16	-

Values are numbers. *= Ratio between the number of correct items and the maximum number of administered items; **= Perseverations are reported as the ratio between perseveration absolute number and the maximum number of cards provided during the test; ***= Verbal fluency indices were obtained as following: time for generation condition - time for control condition (reading or writing generated words)/total number of items generated. -= not applicable. Abbreviations: ALS= Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; ALS-FTD-Q= ALS-FTD questionnaire; BADA= Battery for aphasic deficit analysis; BDI= Beck Depression Inventory; bvFTD= behavioral variant frontotemporal dementia; CDR= Clinical dementia rating scale; CET= Cognitive estimation test; CPM= Colored progressive matrices; CST= Card sorting tests; FBI= Frontal Behavioral Inventory; HDRS= Hamilton Depression Rating Scale; HC= Healthy controls; MMSE= Mini-Mental state examination; NA=not available; PF= Phonemic fluency; PLS= Primary lateral sclerosis; RAVLT= Rey auditory verbal learning test; right-SD= right-sided semantic dementia; SB= Sum of boxes; SF= Semantic fluency; TMT= Trail making test

eTable 5**VBM results – Level 1 (sFTLD vs gFTLD vs HC)**Regions presented in table survived a $p < 0.05$ FWE-corrected at cluster level.

sFTLD < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Inferior frontal gyrus – orbital part (47)	R	48934	27	10	-22	7.71
Cerebellum –Crus I	R	521	32	-72	-38	6.13
Anterior prefrontal cortex (10)	R	1027	39	46	10	6.01
Anterior prefrontal cortex (10)	L	190	-34	51	2	5.88
Cerebellum – Crus I	L	473	-26	-74	-36	5.75
Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (9)	L	256	-15	48	38	5.63
Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (9)	R	438	12	56	30	5.63
Premotor cortex (6)	L	156	-42	-10	36	5.28
Thalamus (50)	L	58	-2	-2	2	5.13
Inferior frontal gyrus (44)	R	129	44	21	18	4.94
Dorsal posterior cingulate cortex (31)	R	119	0	-28	39	4.92
Frontal eye fields (8)	R	39	46	20	38	4.91
Premotor cortex (6)	L	141	-8	6	52	4.91
Secondary visual cortex (18)	L	31	-18	-78	-14	4.91
gFTLD < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Inferior frontal gyrus (47)	R	111322	38	26	-4	7.89
Cerebellum –Crus II	L	1441	-30	-76	-40	6.48
Angular gyrus (39)	R	1178	38	-62	54	5.73
Cerebellum –Crus II	R	1000	27	-80	-38	5.44
Primary visual cortex (17)	L	237	-8	-90	2	5.28
Superior parietal lobule (7)	L	146	-21	-69	36	5.28
Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (46)	L	118	-52	28	21	5.17
Angular gyrus (39)	R	124	44	-70	38	4.96

Middle temporal gyrus (21)	L	49	-60	-15	-20	4.93
Inferior frontal gyrus (44)	L	52	-39	9	24	4.89
gFTLD < sFTLD						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Angular gyrus (39)	L	395	-63	-51	30	5.08

eTable 6**VBM results – Level 2 (sMND vs gMND vs sFTD vs gFTD vs HC)**Regions presented in table survived a $p < 0.05$ FWE-corrected at cluster level.

sMND < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Precentral cortex (4)	L	38	-42	-7	37	5.45
gMND < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Secondary visual cortex (18)	L	224	-10	-68	-8	5.31
Cerebellum - Vermis VIIa		418	2	-60	-33	5.29
Hippocampus (54)	L	112	-21	-15	-12	5.20
Cerebellum – Lobule VIIb	R	332	21	-70	-48	5.19
Inferior temporal gyrus (20)	L	229	-40	-8	-42	5.13
Cerebellum – Crus II	L	231	-28	-75	-39	5.06
Angular gyrus (39)	L	42	-69	-44	20	4.97
Angular gyrus (39)	L	299	-66	-51	28	4.95
Cerebellum – Lobule VIIb	L	183	-26	-70	-48	4.95
Dorsal entorhinal cortex (34)	L	38	-30	3	-16	4.81
Associative visual cortex (19)	R	45	50	-82	-4	4.80
Superior temporal gyrus (22)	L	45	-48	-3	-4	4.77
Rolandic operculum (4)	L	20	-41	-8	14	4.60
sFTD < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Inferior frontal gyrus – orbital part (47)	R	99854	27	10	-22	9.14
Cerebellum – Crus I	R	376	34	-70	-39	5.74
Cerebellum – Crus I	L	410	-30	-74	-36	5.43
Ventral posterior cingulate cortex (23)	L	42	-8	-48	22	4.63
gFTD < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Thalamus (50)	L	88130	-2	-3	4	7.87

Fusiform (37)	L	2439	-50	-60	-18	6.48
Angular gyrus (39)	R	705	39	-57	54	5.75
Angular gyrus (39)	L	1431	-63	-56	33	5.66
Middle temporal gyrus (21)	L	108	-57	-38	-20	5.31
Angular gyrus (39)	R	654	36	-69	36	5.27
Fusiform (37)	R	293	26	-57	-12	5.24
Associative visual cortex (19)	L	108	-28	-72	-12	5.16
Primary sensory (1)	R	158	60	-15	39	5.09
sMND > gMND						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (9)	L	73	-4	50	22	5.14
Angular gyrus (39)	L	54	-66	-44	22	4.84
sFTD > gFTD						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Thalamus (50)	L	457	-6	-4	10	3.84
Superior parietal lobule (7)	R	377	27	-64	48	3.80
Angular gyrus (39)	L	846	-54	-58	28	3.78
Thalamus (50)	R	452	16	-30	8	3.64
Superior parietal lobule (7)	L	201	-22	-69	39	3.60
Superior parietal lobule (5)	L	189	-28	-39	58	3.55
Dorsal posterior cingulate cortex (31)	R	185	9	-33	40	3.47
Associative visual cortex (19)	L	35	-28	-87	33	3.28

eTable 7**VBM results – Level 3 (C9-MND vs C9-FTD vs GRN vs TARDBP vs SOD1 vs sMND vs sFTD vs HC)**Regions presented in table survived a $p < 0.05$ FWE-corrected at cluster level.

C9-MND < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Primary motor cortex (4)	L	1766	-39	-16	44	6.76
Ventral posterior cingulate cortex (23)	L	10464	-12	-62	9	6.71
Associative visual cortex (19)	R	330	48	-82	-9	5.92
Primary Auditory (41)	R	1195	63	-4	8	5.89
Cerebellum – Lobule V	L	1202	-4	-66	-48	5.61
Putamen (49)	L	926	-26	-4	-10	5.60
Ventral anterior cingulate cortex (24)	L	368	-15	-15	39	5.58
Superior parietal lobule (7)	L	986	-36	-45	50	5.50
Cerebellum – Lobule VIIIb	L	418	-15	-50	-52	5.48
Orbitofrontal area (11)	L	137	-21	54	-21	5.46
Angular gyrus (39)	R	516	42	-57	52	5.34
C9-FTD < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Insula (13)	R	182058	50	4	-2	8.40
Cerebellum – Crus II	L	669	-32	-78	-36	5.98
Cerebellum – Lobule IX	R	467	2	-46	-45	5.47
Primary Motor (4)	R	197	32	-27	50	5.40
Angular gyrus (39)	L	52	-36	-72	44	5.04
GRN < HC						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Anterior prefrontal cortex (10)	R	62052	22	51	-14	7.51
Thalamus (50)	L	1344	0	-2	4	6.49
Angular gyrus (39)	L	2524	-57	-52	42	6.45
Fusiform (37)	L	776	-51	-46	-21	5.72
Caudate (48)	R	595	8	14	14	5.65
Superior temporal gyrus (22)	R	1293	51	-24	-6	5.49
Middle temporal gyrus (21)	L	345	-63	-22	-9	5.45
Inferior temporal gyrus (20)	L	79	-48	-8	-34	5.06
Premotor cortex (6)	L	49	-50	-8	24	5.05
Cerebellum – Crus II	R	197	32	-75	-39	5.00

C9-MND < sMND						
Anatomic regions (BA)	Side	Cluster size	MNI coordinates			T values
			x	y	z	
Superior parietal lobule (7)	L	107	-39	-44	48	5.25
Orbitofrontal area (11)	L	56	-21	54	-21	5.06
Inferior frontal gyrus (44)	R	97	54	15	14	5.02
Visual association (18)	R	45	2	-93	18	4.94
Thalamus (50)	R	171	3	-15	9	4.83

eTable 8. Subcortical, hippocampal and cerebellar grey matter volumes in healthy controls and FTL D patients classified by genetic status.

	HC	sFTLD	gFTLD	p HC vs sFTLD	p HC vs gFTLD	p sFTLD vs gFTLD
Left Caudate	4307.65 ± 447.97 (3452.28 - 5421.81)	4118.96 ± 557.54 (2690.60 - 6181.46)	3930.99 ± 559.67 (2571.00 - 5337.44)	0.283	< 0.001	0.071
Right Caudate	4612.60 ± 407.24 (3787.15 - 5613.63)	4362.45 ± 676.53 (3056.91 - 6392.30)	4175.41 ± 660.32 (2348.50 - 5703.71)	0.077	< 0.001	0.049
Left Putamen	6129.14 ± 544.38 (4696.78 - 7348.50)	5731.35 ± 936.31 (3853.59 - 9961.50)	5633.20 ± 817.77 (3280.95 - 7692.93)	0.037	0.002	1.000
Right Putamen	5999.96 ± 577.73 (4791.13 - 7405.07)	5640.19 ± 699.89 (3255.61 - 7125.57)	5635.21 ± 1113.31 (3192.21 - 11772.49)	0.049	0.037	1.000
Left Pallidum	2327.81 ± 302.04 (1672.99 - 3306.62)	2320.30 ± 445.65 (1087.44 - 3926.37)	2254.02 ± 363.61 (1509.96 - 3302.99)	1.000	1.000	0.836
Right Pallidum	2324.39 ± 328.51 (1816.68 - 3383.09)	2273.42 ± 395.80 (1577.88 - 3789.68)	2231.27 ± 330.08 (1323.85 - 3200.47)	1.000	0.593	1.000
Left Thalamus	10214.62 ± 817.16 (8596.19 - 12191.74)	9897.77 ± 796.94 (7433.40 - 11596.03)	9522.75 ± 1054.81 (6014.01 - 12139.69)	0.056	< 0.001	0.018
Right Thalamus	9992.55 ± 791.78 (8135.10 - 11756.69)	9567.91 ± 923.86 (7014.78 - 11278.02)	9188.95 ± 1057.02 (5887.97 - 11523.94)	0.006	< 0.001	0.021
Left Hippocampus	4940.79 ± 605.41 (3280.98 - 6015.97)	4539.48 ± 701.38 (3032.31 - 6805.9)	4576.63 ± 694.89 (2694.10 - 5657.84)	0.003	0.004	1.000
Right Hippocampus	4875.95 ± 676.59 (2575.05 - 6227.41)	4618.66 ± 728.06 (2300.78 - 6025.76)	4593.01 ± 689.18 (2898.13 - 5714.81)	0.120	0.056	1.000
Left Amygdala	1828.65 ± 269.39 (1257.58 - 2485.23)	1711.40 ± 245.19 (1205.88 - 2216.55)	1753.83 ± 274.82 (1188.39 - 2397.40)	0.015	0.191	0.847
Right Amygdala	1718.00 ± 324.25 (846.45 - 2275.43)	1681.02 ± 368.41 (970.30 - 3246.56)	1769.00 ± 277.34 (921.83 - 2486.86)	1.000	1.000	0.301
Left I-IV	4224.53 ± 466.39 (2175.12 - 5128.73)	4139.88 ± 476.42 (1433.91 - 5055.45)	4200.69 ± 415.61 (3215.17 - 5236.53)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right I-IV	4835.00 ± 454.31 (2810.96 - 5719.95)	4741.481 ± 509.26 (2121.52 - 5746.22)	4820.72 ± 472.62 (3734.50 - 5966.44)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left V	5519.82 ± 637.48 (2396.54 - 6857.00)	5368.79 ± 667.27 (1432.51 - 6560.12)	5580.97 ± 614.52 (4456.44 - 7287.30)	0.984	1.000	0.277

Right V	5394.18 ± 556.73 (2686.64 - 6359.12)	5239.75 ± 625.25 (1769.33 - 6547.83)	5418.98 ± 571.60 (4283.85 - 6997.50)	0.778	1.000	0.372
Left VI	12238.89 ± 1483.53 (4570.48 - 15128.63)	11892.84 ± 1547.33 (3111.00 - 14900.48)	12111.77 ± 1357.43 (546.34 - 15681.68)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis VI	2508.21 ± 288.01 (1194.72 - 3089.37)	2471.27 ± 276.14 (1102.69 - 2955.84)	2473.84 ± 250.00 (2052.09 - 3043.57)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right VI	10669.18 ± 1141.67 (5130.54 - 12436.81)	10485.02 ± 1341.10 (3143.14 - 13816.95)	10717.70 ± 1189.72 (8126.65 - 13323.82)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left Crus I	17988.07 ± 2144.14 (6579.83 - 21373.06)	17492.53 ± 2131.84 (5667.16 - 20753.11)	17675.63 ± 1789.84 (14215.09 - 22365.30)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis Crus I	27.38 ± 5.92 (16.01 - 40.41)	27.57 ± 5.28 (15.37 - 37.62)	28.65 ± 5.97 (15.60 - 42.93)	1.000	0.998	0.669
Right Crus I	17517.67 ± 1713.27 (9367.11 - 19876.71)	17271.61 ± 2239.97 (6294.67 - 20454.22)	17201.69 ± 1785.86 (13659.18 - 20709.32)	1.000	0.786	1.000
Left Crus II	13395.10 ± 1337.00 (9208.45 - 16246.67)	13215.49 ± 1269.50 (8863.41 - 15346.39)	12909.04 ± 1299.24 (10549.02 - 17237.69)	1.000	0.203	0.307
Vermis Crus II	543.66 ± 55.28 (391.92 - 638.49)	533.44 ± (45.55 - 403.90)	528.32 ± 65.05 (376.50 - 656.91)	1.000	0.582	1.000
Right Crus II	12608.73 ± 1116.27 (10445.79 - 14676.75)	12274.16 ± 1146.49 (10011.94 - 15300.30)	11897.10 ± 1166.38 (9704.90 - 15349.60)	0.845	0.005	0.103
Left VIIb	6777.29 ± 640.83 (5336.57 - 8326.35)	6638.53 ± 647.11 (5367.83 - 7935.25)	6461.75 ± 725.244 (5205.39 - 8710.30)	1.000	0.071	0.185
Vermis VIIb	240.72 ± 36.27 (133.80 - 345.67)	224.84 ± 28.41 (117.40 - 271.23)	227.83 ± 36.40 (166.60 - 322.00)	0.186	0.222	1.000
Right VIIb	6836.78 ± 608.77 (5483.39 - 8184.08)	6708.94 ± 615.19 (5269.95 - 7736.57)	6460.69 ± 689.35 (5075.90 - 8459.36)	1.000	0.008	0.038
Left VIIIa	7059.44 ± 699.10 (4501.80 - 8682.68)	6938.96 ± 695.65 (4976.76 - 8751.78)	6791.95 ± 752.10 (5492.15 - 8847.86)	1.000	0.241	0.374
Vermis VIIIa	1547.16 ± 188.00 (792.14 - 1925.24)	1471.89 ± 162.91 (890.25 - 1800.20)	1505.47 ± 182.37 (1228.62 - 1998.04)	0.169	0.768	1.000
Right VIIIa	6483.28 ± 688.87 (3506.01 - 7656.93)	6425.38 ± 651.41 (4092.09 - 7720.46)	6214.36 ± 638.84 (4962.37 - 7939.34)	1.000	0.131	0.113
Left VIIIb	5661.24 ± 580.55 (3111.71 - 6628.33)	5581.13 ± 573.98 (3802.80 - 6705.26)	5521.39 ± 593.23 (4418.25 - 7263.622)	1.000	0.868	1.000
Vermis VIIIb	776.80 ± 81.73 (428.63 - 940.87)	764.04 ± 83.20 (470.98 - 950.26)	758.36 ± 98.67 (562.38 - 1031.06)	1.000	1.000	1.000

Right VIIIb	5400.34 ± 502.96 (3105.79 - 6132.71)	5317.03 ± 503.58 (3352.78 - 6144.61)	5288.62 ± 541.36 (4194.78 - 6498.71)	1.000	0.915	1.000
Left IX	4369.81 ± 486.42 (2600.20 - 5269.52)	4305.42 ± 442.06 (3284.17 - 5259.16)	4269.57 ± 492.66 (3289.08 - 5390.65)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis IX	915.68 ± 115.59 (504.41 - 1202.48)	891.38 ± 106.01 (651.56 - 1136.25)	894.93 ± 121.37 (709.83 - 1178.14)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right IX	4571.85 ± 525.48 (2627.43 - 5465.87)	4458.41 ± 440.48 (3595.61 - 5440.52)	4483.68 ± 507.82 (3509.57 - 5598.73)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left X	918.90 ± 100.54 (472.44 - 1122.37)	917.86 ± 100.41 (725.94 - 1166.27)	916.96 ± 94.21 (750.58- 1179.11)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis X	489.09 ± 68.21 (320.88 - 655.32)	518.39 ± 86.18 (338.21 - 714.89)	522.31 ± 84.94 (369.31 - 870.97)	0.121	0.056	1.000
Right X	902.45 ± 103.20 (468.89 - 1140.85)	903.74 ± 114.62 (422.07 - 1104.78)	913.36 ± 89.30 (734.38 - 1114.11)	1.000	1.000	1.000

Values (mm³) are reported as means ± standard deviations [range]. P values refer to age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. Abbreviations: HC= healthy control; sFTLD= sporadic frontotemporal lobar degeneration; gFTLD= genetic frontotemporal lobar degeneration.

eTable 9. Subcortical, hippocampal and cerebellar grey matter volumes in healthy controls and FTLD patients classified by clinical presentation and genetic status.

	HC	sMND	gMND	p HC vs sMND	p HC vs gMND	p sMND vs gMND	sFTD	gFTD	p HC vs sFTD	p HC vs gFTD	P sFTD vs gFTD
Left Caudate	4307.65 ± 447.97 (3452.28 - 5421.81)	4233.82 ± 73.16 (4089.36 - 4378.28)	4016.33 ± 472.36 (3248.37 - 5200.69)	0.893	0.163	0.010	3795.91 ± 122.70 (3553.64 - 4038.18)	3708.04 ± 732.45 (2571.00 - 5337.44)	<0.001	<0.001	1.000
Right Caudate	4612.60 ± 407.24 (3787.15 - 5613.63)	4527.55 ± 80.50 (4368.60 - 4686.50)	4273.52 ± 584.39 (3104.00 - 5703.71)	1.000	0.102	0.132	3898.10 ± 1345.00 (3631.53 - 4164.66)	3921.66 ± 813.04 (2348.50 - 5454.66)	<0.001	<0.001	1.000
Left Putamen	6129.14 ± 544.38 (4696.78 - 7348.50)	5802.01 ± 114.70 (5575.51 - 6028.50)	5752.66 ± 701.28 (4345.15 - 7372.00)	1.000	0.066	0.592	5532.64 ± 192.36 (5152.79 - 5912.48)	5300.53 ± 1054.18 (3280.95 - 7692.93)	0.020	<0.001	1.000
Right Putamen	5999.96 ± 577.73 (4791.13 - 7405.07)	5810.34 ± 121.69 (5570.05 - 6050.63)	5694.41 ± 678.09 (3764.58 - 6876.74)	1.000	0.280	1.000	5161.65 ± 204.08 (4758.67 - 5564.64)	5460.58 ± 1908.05 (3192.21 - 11772.49)	0.030	0.043	1.000
Left Pallidum	2327.81 ± 302.04 (1672.99 - 3306.62)	2392.86 ± 54.57 (2285.11 - 2500.60)	2122.66 ± 358.56 (1547.20 - 3302.99)	0.090	1.000	0.250	2116.23 ± 91.51 (1935.53 - 2296.93)	2122.66 ± 358.55 (1509.96 - 2914.51)	0.024	0.044	1.000
Right Pallidum	2324.39 ± 328.51 (1816.68 - 3383.09)	2334.04 ± 51.22 (2232.89 - 2435.18)	2245.68 ± 337.74 (1323.86 - 3200.47)	0.306	1.000	0.416	2102.96 ± 85.90 (1933.33 - 2272.58)	2180.27 ± 319.74 (1680.55 - 3092.89)	0.010	0.017	1.000
Left Thalamus	10214.62 ± 817.16 (8596.19 - 12191.74)	10140.60 ± 113.560 (9916.29 - 10364.91)	9777.35 ± 872.32 (8157.97 - 12139.69)	1.000	0.017	0.032	9214.83 ± 190.51 (8838.65 - 9591.00)	8770.36 ± 1211.83 (6014.01 - 11089.68)	0.001	<0.001	0.390

Right Thalamus	9992.55 ± 791.78 (8135.10 - 11756.69)	9841.19 ± 118.24 (9607.72 - 10074.67)	9500.30 ± 907.43 (7560.34 - 11523.94)	1.000	0.008	0.090	8799.30 ± 198.29 (8407.76 - 9190.85)	8263.01 ± 937.46 (5887.97 - 9801.73)	<0.001	<0.001	0.172
Left Hippocampus	4940.79 ± 605.41 (3280.98 - 6015.97)	4674.49 ± 92.94 (4490.96 - 4858.02)	4694.09 ± 552.20 (3179.22 - 5628.55)	0.371	0.471	1.000	4159.78 ± 155.87 (3852.00 - 4467.56)	4225.12 ± 941.33 (2694.10 - 5657.84)	<0.001	<0.001	1.000
Right Hippocampus	4875.9 5± 676.59 (2575.05 - 6227.41)	4778.28 ± 97.83 (4585.09 - 4971.46)	4768.97 ± 535.46 (3773.09 - 5714.81)	1.000	1.000	1.000	4169.75 ± 164.07 (3845.77 - 4493.73)	4078.00 ± 840.62 (2898.13 - 5437.71)	0.004	0.001	1.000
Left Amygdala	1828.65 ± 269.39 (1257.58 - 2485.23)	1754.91 ± 38.35 (1679.19 - 1830.64)	1782.55 ± 263.47 (1197.67 - 2397.40)	0.112	1.121	1.000	1589.02 ± 64.32 (1462.02 - 1716.02)	1687.90 ± 302.71 (1188.39 - 2199.88)	0.037	0.573	0.628
Right Amygdala	1718.00 ± 324.25 (846.45 - 2275.43)	1756.29 ± 47.13 (1663.22 - 1849.36)	1785.39 ± 231.80 (1224.26 - 2169.62)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1469.34 ± 79.05 (1313.26 - 1625.42)	1709.81 ± 383.55 (921.83 - 2486.86)	0.148	1.000	0.088
Left I-IV	4224.53 ± 466.39 (2175.12 - 5128.73)	4101.63 ± 516.97 (1433.90 - 4798.41)	4144.58 ± 363.87 (3215.16 - 4896.71)	0.441	0.817	1.000	4235.49 ± 351.72 (3794.45 - 5055.45)	4333.21 ± 522.62 (3411.94 - 5236.53)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right I-IV	4835.00 ± 454.31 (2810.96 - 5719.95)	4675.49 ± 520.08 (2121.51 - 5374.03)	4742.41 ± 429.74 (3734.50 - 5612.77)	0.341	0.986	1.000	4906.44 ± 455.01 (4279.04 - 5746.21)	5003.22 ± 536.88 (4223.44 - 5966.43)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left V	5519.82 ± 637.48 (2396.54 - 6857.00)	5302.20 ± 716.17 (1432.51 - 6035.71)	5526.54 ± 548.20 (4456.44 - 6681.43)	0.150	1.000	0.242	5535.25 ± 507.60 (4827.28 - 6560.12)	5716.89 ± 783.83 (4837.93 - 7287.29)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right V	5394.18 ± 556.73 (2686.64 - 6359.12)	5164.01 ± 646.51 (1769.32 - 5863.51)	5362.17 ± 527.23 (4283.84 - 6690.80)	0.091	0.278	1.000	5429.06 ± 541.44 (4730.82 - 6547.82)	5564.97 ± 688.05 (4840.21 - 6997.49)	1.000	1.000	1.000

Left VI	12238.89 ± 1483.53 (4570.48 - 15128.63)	11677.95 ± ± 1636.25 (3110.99 - 13296.96)	11998.54 ± 1246.71 (9546.33 - 14262.05)	0.224	1.000	0.901	12430.06 ± 1177.61 (11010.10 - 14900.47)	12387.28 ± 1660.76 (9821.44 - 15681.68)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis VI	2508.21 ± 288.01 (1194.72 - 3089.37)	2450.65 ± 294.26 (1102.68 - 2795.82)	2456.74 ± 239.37 (2052.08 - 2920.22)	1.000	1.000	1.000	2522.81 ± 224.72 (2195.92 - 2955.83)	2515.12 ± 286.28 (2138.37 - 3043.56)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right VI	10669.18 ± 1141.67 (5130.54 - 12436.81)	10291.03 ± ± 1373.58 (3143.14 - 12226.63)	10702.29 ± 1123.85 (8126.65 - 13323.82)	0.178	1.000	0.265	10969.97 ± 1156.69 (9613.10 - 13816.94)	10754.24 ± 1423.97 (8706.82 - 13159.07)	0.829	1.000	1.000
Left Crus I	17988.07 ± 2144.14 (6579.83 - 21373.06)	17384.04 ± ± 2295.39 (5667.15 - 20296.89)	17482.33 ± 1677.59 (14215.08 - 20808.86)	0.639	0.809	1.000	17763.73 ± 1689.76 (13774.84 - 20753.11)	18212.34 ± 2075.34 (15136.47 - 22365.30)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis Crus I	27.38 ± 5.92 (16.01 - 40.41)	27.63 ± 4.86 (15.37 - 37.62)	28.913 ± 6.32 (15.60 - 42.93)	1.000	1.000	0.973	27.40 ± 6.37 (16.06 - 35.40)	28.32 ± 4.96 (21.26 - 41.28)	1.000	0.383	1.000
Right Crus I	17517.67 ± 1713.27 (9367.11 - 19876.71)	17350.72 ± ± 2341.86 (6294.66 - 20112.91)	17257.60 ± 1708.51 (13918.91 - 20709.31)	0.674	0.506	1.000	17073.84 ± 2019.81 (13952.77 - 20454.22)	17088.64 ± 2076.29 (13659.17 - 20679.38)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left Crus II	13395.10 ± 1337.00 (9208.45 - 16246.67)	13146.82 ± ± 1305.75 (8863.41 - 15346.39)	12803.41 ± 1156.06 (10887.73 - 14996.43)	1.000	0.104	0.316	13387.16 ± 1196.79 (11158.75 - 15290.59)	13186.06 ± 1670.73 (10549.01 - 17237.68)	1.000	0.904	1.000
Vermis Crus II	543.66 ± 55.28 (391.92 - 638.49)	529.92 ± 45.00 (403.89 - 607.39)	522.30 ± 65.53 (376.5 - 656.91)	1.000	0.578	1.000	542.23 ± 47.17 (450.65 - 614.57)	542.46 ± 64.42 (435.51 - 645.48)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right Crus II	12608.73 ± 1116.27	12274.48 ± ± 1089.25	11861.13 ± 1079.68	1.000	0.017	0.070	12273.34 ± 1317.10	11940.70 ± 1424.13	1.000	0.087	1.000

	(10445.79 - 14676.75)	(10011.93 - 14671.86)	(10131.02 - 14323.13)				(10251.54 - 15300.30)	(9704.90 - 15349.59)			
Left VIIb	6777.29 ± 640.83 (5336.57 - 8326.35)	6579.04 ± 654.86 (5367.82 - 7808.39)	6398.95 ± 679.80 (5240.30 - 7874.31)	1.000	0.077	0.225	6787.21 ± 622.39 (5692.55 - 7935.25)	6611.28 ± 854.09 (5205.38 - 8710.29)	1.000	0.443	1.000
Vermis VIIb	240.72 ± 36.27 (133.80 - 345.67)	220.32 ± 28.44 (117.39 - 263.82)	223.32 ± 35.17 (166.59 - 298.21)	0.189	0.250	1.000	236.14 ± 25.80 (196.04 -271.23)	239.34 ± 39.05 (181.51 - 321.98)	1.000	0.811	1.000
Right VIIb	6836.78 ± 608.77 (5483.39 - 8184.08)	6688.17 ± 617.31 (5269.94 - 7660.55)	6418.02 ± 657.11 (5075.89 - 7784.29)	1.000	0.019	0.085	6760.85 ± 626.77 (5778.92 - 7736.56)	6528.72 ± 777.25 (5325.27 - 8459.36)	1.000	0.067	1.000
Left VIIIa	7059.44 ± 699.10 (4501.80 - 8682.68)	6834.44 ± 667.90 (4976.7 ± 7938.36)	6711.19 ± 721.78 (5492.14 - 8418.51)	1.000	0.139	0.798	7200.25 ± 715.96 (6229.92 - 8751.78)	6975.92 ± 825.73 (5607.87 - 8847.86)	1.000	0.865	0.914
Vermis VIIIa	1547.16 ± 188.00 (792.14 - 1925.24)	1457.86 ± 174.96 (890.25 - 1800.19)	1490.34 ± 165.81 (1228.61 - 1804.51)	0.088	0.408	1.000	1506.94 ± 126.00 (1258.32 - 1693.58)	1549.36 ± 226.27 (1228.84 - 1998.03)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right VIIIa	6483.28 ± 688.87 (3506.01 - 7656.93)	6370.20 ± 680.84 (4092.09 - 7720.46)	6161.04 ± 614.52 (4962.37 - 7612.67)	1.000	0.092	0.333	6563.34 ± 567.68 (5818.53 - 7589.59)	6303.56 ± 684.68 (5259.21 - 7939.34)	1.000	0.558	0.689
Left VIIIb	5661.24 ± 580.55 (3111.71 - 6628.33)	5484.83 ± 551.13 (3802.79 - 6482.95)	5473.35 ± 573.10 (4418.24 - 6946.41)	1.000	0.611	1.000	5821.86 ± 575.93 (4878.75 - 6705.25)	5628.72 ± 657.75 (4691.71 - 7263.62)	1.000	1.000	0.895
Vermis VIIIb	776.80 ± 81.73 (428.63 - 940.87)	756.36 ± 90.65 (470.98 - 950.25)	748.00 ± 93.07 (562.37 - 950.37)	1.000	0.498	1.000	783.22 ± 58.82 (673.25 - 866.99)	785.73 ± 113.56 (616.57 - 1031.05)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right VIIIb	5400.34 ± 502.96	5258.81 ± 499.73	5268.44 ± 537.08	0.708	0.681	1.000	5462.55 ± 498.92	5314.02 ± 569.56	1.000	1.000	1.000

	(3105.79 - 6132.71)	(3352.77 - 6103.33)	(4194.79 - 6430.70)				(4510.07 - 6144.61)	(4434.56 - 6498.71)			
Left IX	4369.81 ± 486.42 (2600.20 - 5269.52)	4283.77 ± 448.41 (3284.17 - 5259.15)	4254.31 ± 475.34 (3289.08 - 5293.86)	1.000	1.000	1.000	4359.53 ± 435.15 (3615.10 - 5052.50)	4282.48 ± 552.20 (3561.14 - 5390.65)	1.000	0.867	1.000
Vermis IX	915.68 ± 115.59 (504.41 - 1202.48)	878.48 ± 107.19 (651.55 - 1136.24)	884.64 ± 112.05 (709.8 - 1097.0)	1.000	1.000	1.000	923.62 ± 98.88 (770.64 - 1076.22)	923.81 ± 147.02 (737.62 - 1178.14)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Right IX	4571.85 ± 525.48 (2627.43 - 5465.87)	4431.04 ± 432.24 (3595.61 - 5367.82)	4448.26 ± 473.69 (3509.56 - 5598.73)	1.000	1.000	1.000	4526.81 ± 467.62 (3763.81 - 5440.52)	4548.00 ± 598.30 (3637.77 - 5591.70)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Left X	918.90 ± 100.54 (472.44 - 1122.37)	914.79 ± 98.05 (725.94 - 1100.64)	913.79 ± 93.75 (750.57 - 1097.82)	1.000	1.000	1.000	925.49 ± 109.02 (771.38 - 1166.27)	921.55 ± 99.34 (788.03 - 1179.11)	1.000	1.000	1.000
Vermis X	489.09 ± 68.21 (320.88 - 655.32)	507.85 ± 85.13 (338.21 - 709.38)	510.47 ± 69.02 (369.30 - 679.55)	0.645	0.547	1.000	544.71 ± 85.73 (391.78 - 714.88)	548.81 ± 115.37 (409.82 - 870.97)	0.104	0.094	1.000
Right X	902.45 ± 103.20 (468.89 - 1140.85)	901.31 ± 120.72 (422.06 - 1104.77)	910.27 ± 90.61 (734.38 - 1102.65)	1.000	1.000	1.000	909.77 ± 101.10 (714.02 - 1069.86)	921.69 ± 90.50 (795.22 - 1114.10)	1.000	0.974	1.000

Values (mm³) are reported as means ± standard deviations [min. value – max. value]. P values refer to age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. Abbreviations: HC= healthy control; sMND= sporadic motor neuron disease; sFTD= sporadic frontotemporal dementia; gMND= genetic motor neuron disease; gFTD= genetic frontotemporal dementia.

eTable 10. Subcortical, hippocampal and cerebellar grey matter volumes in healthy controls and FTLN patients classified by clinical presentation and genotype.

	HC	sMND	C9-MND	SOD1	TARDBP	p ^{MND}	sFTD	C9-FTD	GRN	p ^{FTD}
Left Caudate	4307.65 ± 68.10 (4173.27 – 4442.04)	4233.82 ± 73.16 (4089.36 – 4378.28)	3864.43 ± 104.63 (3657.82 – 4071.04)	4467.71 ± 185.49 (4101.44 – 4834.00)	4093.39 ± 155.19 (3786.94 – 4399.83)	0.001	3795.91 ± 122.70 (3553.64 – 4038.18)	3653.68 ± 148.00 (3361.49 – 3945.864)	3910.89 ± 173.51 (3568.27 – 4253.51)	<0.001
Right Caudate	4612.60 ± 74.88 (4464.73 – 4760.46)	4527.55 ± 80.50 (4368.60 – 4686.50)	4203.81 ± 115.13 (3976.48 – 4431.14)	4897.08 ± 204.09 (4494.07 – 5300.09)	4291.27 ± 170.76 (3954.09 – 4628.45)	0.007	3898.10 ± 1345.00 (3631.53 – 4164.66)	3872.27 ± 162.81 (3550.78 – 4193.76)	4028.22 ± 190.90 (3651.24 – 4405.20)	<0.001
Left Putamen	6129.14 ± 106.70 (5918.44 – 6339.84)	5802.01 ± 114.70 (5575.51 – 6028.50)	5769.75 ± 164.05 (5445.82 – 6093.68)	6120.68 ± 290.83 (5546.41 – 6694.95)	5794.31 ± 243.32 (5313.84 – 6274.78)	0.127	5532.64 ± 192.36 (5152.79 – 5912.48)	5467.32 ± 232.00 (5009.21 – 5925.43)	5180.66 ± 272.04 (4643.48 – 5717.84)	0.001
Right Putamen	5999.96 ± 113.20 (5776.43 – 6223.50)	5810.34 ± 121.69 (5570.05 – 6050.63)	5812.01 ± 174.04 (5468.34 – 6155.67)	6045.98 ± 308.54 (5436.73 – 6655.24)	5700.60 ± 258.15 (5190.86 – 6210.34)	0.501	5161.65 ± 204.08 (4758.67 – 5564.64)	5586.28 ± 246.13 (5100.26 – 6072.29)	5230.31 ± 288.62 (4660.40 – 5800.22)	0.035
Left Pallidum	2327.81 ± 50.76 (2227.58 – 2428.05)	2392.86 ± 54.57 (2285.11 – 2500.60)	2207.37 ± 78.04 (2053.27 – 2361.46)	2411.67 ± 138.35 (2138.48 – 2684.86)	2391.33 ± 115.75 (2162.77 – 2619.9)	0.127	2116.23 ± 91.51 (1935.53 – 2296.93)	2151.36 ± 110.37 (1933.43 – 2369.29)	2153.55 ± 129.41 (1898.00 – 2409.09)	0.022
Right Pallidum	2324.39 ± 47.65 (2230.3 – 2418.48)	2334.04 ± 51.22 (2232.89 – 2435.18)	2187.33 ± 73.26 (2042.67 – 2331.99)	2440.47 ± 129.87 (2184.02 – 2696.92)	2295.78 ± 108.66 (2081.22 – 2510.35)	0.147	2102.96 ± 85.90 (1933.33 – 2272.58)	2102.08 ± 103.60 (1897.50 – 2306.65)	2109.89 ± 121.49 (1870.00 – 2349.78)	0.004
Left Thalamus	10214.62 ± 105.67 (10005.95 – 10423.29)	10140.60 ± 113.560 (9916.29 – 10364.91)	9591.92 ± 162.46 (9271.11 – 9912.72)	10443.54 ± 288.02 (9874.81 – 11012.26)	10004.01 ± 240.97 (9528.18 – 10479.84)	<0.001	9214.83 ± 190.51 (8838.65 – 9591.00)	8997.07 ± 229.76 (8543.39 – 9450.76)	8799.17 ± 269.42 (8267.17 – 9331.16)	<0.001
Right Thalamus	9992.55 ± 109.99 (9775.36 – 10209.74)	9841.19 ± 118.24 (9607.72 – 10074.67)	9362.10 ± 169.10 (9028.19 – 9696.01)	10156.31 ± 299.78 (9564.35 – 10748.27)	9698.09 ± 250.82 (9202.82 – 10193.36)	0.001	8799.30 ± 198.29 (8407.76 – 9190.85)	8476.12 ± 239.14 (8003.90 – 8948.33)	8421.24 ± 280.42 (7867.52 – 8974.97)	<0.001
Left Hippocampus	4940.79 ± 86.46	4674.49 ± 92.94	4655.52 ± 132.93	5150.93 ± 235.65	4783.75 ± 197.16	0.199	4159.78 ± 155.87	4407.30 ± 187.99	3973.59 ± 220.43	<0.001

	(4770.06 - 5111.52)	(4490.96 - 4858.02)	(4393.04 - 4918.00)	(4685.60 - 5616.25)	(4394.44 - 5173.07)		(3852.00 - 4467.56)	(4036.09 - 4778.50)	(3538.32 - 4408.86)	
Right Hippocampus	4875.95 ± 91.01 (4696.25 - 5055.66)	4778.28 ± 97.83 (4585.09 - 4971.46)	4770.49 ± 139.92 (4494.21 - 5046.78)	5105.08 ± 248.05 (4615.28 - 5594.89)	4846.56 ± 207.53 (4436.76 - 5256.36)	0.876	4169.75 ± 164.07 (3845.77 - 4493.73)	4447.94 ± 197.88 (4057.21 - 4838.67)	4002.89 ± 232.03 (3544.72 - 4461.06)	0.001
Left Amygdala	1828.65 ± 35.68 (1758.20 - 1899.10)	1754.91 ± 38.35 (1679.19 - 1830.64)	1793.33 ± 54.85 (1685.02 - 1901.63)	1927.08 ± 97.24 (1735.08 - 2119.09)	1684.46 ± 81.35 (1523.82 - 1845.11)	0.091	1589.02 ± 64.32 (1462.02 - 1716.02)	1795.71 ± 77.57 (1642.55 - 1948.88)	1664.48 ± 90.96 (1484.87 - 1844.08)	0.078
Right Amygdala	1718.00 ± 43.85 (1631.42 - 1804.58)	1756.29 ± 47.13 (1663.22 - 1849.36)	1789.44 ± 67.41 (1656.33 - 1922.55)	1808.20 ± 119.50 (1572.22 - 2044.17)	1830.90 ± 99.99 (1633.47 - 2028.33)	0.931	1469.34 ± 79.05 (1313.26 - 1625.42)	1783.55 ± 95.33 (1595.31 - 1971.80)	1633.12 ± 111.79 (1412.37 - 1853.84)	0.117
Left I-IV	4224.53 ± 466.39 (2175.12 - 5128.73)	4101.63 ± 516.97 (1433.90 - 4798.41)	4060.73 ± 386.57 (3215.16 - 4648.53)	4337.49 ± 345.20 (3871.92 - 4896.71)	4158.52 ± 305.63 (3633.66 - 4752.55)	0.399	4235.49 ± 351.72 (3794.45 - 5055.45)	4303.60 ± 570.96 (3411.94 - 5160.87)	4207.25 ± 370.72 (3841.34 - 4804.46)	0.804
Right I-IV	4835.00 ± 454.31 (2810.96 - 5719.95)	4675.49 ± 520.08 (2121.51 - 5374.03)	4666.51 ± 416.10 (3734.50 - 5398.62)	4948.14 ± 428.11 (4405.01 - 5572.3)	4740.04 ± 350.92 (4089.25 - 5236.20)	0.401	4906.44 ± 455.01 (4279.04 - 5746.21)	4957.69 ± 648.90 (4072.83 - 5966.43)	4839.91 ± 447.24 (4456.97 - 5756.75)	0.732
Left V	5519.82 ± 637.48 (2396.54 - 6857.00)	5302.20 ± 716.17 (1432.51 - 6035.71)	5410.12 ± 536.24 (4560.93 - 6466.83)	5882.04 ± 536.55 (5210.63 - 6681.43)	5528.30 ± 487.04 (4456.44 - 6362.11)	0.165	5535.25 ± 507.60 (4827.28 - 6560.12)	5729.39 ± 845.54 (4673.10 - 7287.29)	5451.61 ± 486.34 (4837.93 - 6183.34)	0.534
Right V	5394.18 ± 556.73 (2686.64 - 6359.12)	5164.01 ± 646.51 (1769.32 - 5863.51)	5226.50 ± 494.01 (4283.84 - 6223.12)	5703.13 ± 483.12 (5036.87 - 6308.19)	5374.96 ± 493.97 (4453.04 - 6248.98)	0.097	5429.06 ± 541.44 (4730.82 - 6547.82)	5574.60 ± 733.52 (4819.29 - 6997.49)	5320.16 ± 447.14 (4857.91 - 6129.58)	0.576
Left VI	12238.89 ± 1483.53 (4570.48 - 15128.63)	11677.95 ± 1636.25 (3110.99 - 13296.96)	11761.03 ± 1263.72 (9546.33 - 14048.83)	12579.01 ± 1301.80 (10552.39 - 14083.73)	12100.87 ± 1261.78 (9705.91 - 14222.38)	0.369	12430.06 ± 1177.61 (11010.10 - 14900.47)	12265.46 ± 1712.16 (9821.44 - 14862.83)	12088.79 ± 1236.64 (10530.52 - 14262.05)	0.870
Vermis VI	2508.21 ± 288.01 (1194.72 - 3089.37)	2450.65 ± 294.26 (1102.68 - 2795.82)	2409.56 ± 237.69 (2052.08 - 2887.40)	2576.29 ± 254.66 (2248.89 - 2920.22)	2484.97 ± 269.22 (2132.50 - 2811.08)	0.730	2522.81 ± 224.72 (2195.92 - 2955.83)	2510.93 ± 264.99 (2173.59 - 2969.38)	2453.03 ± 246.48 (2138.37 - 2848.70)	0.825
Right VI	10669.18 ± 1141.67 (5130.54 - 12436.81)	10291.03 ± 1373.58 (3143.14 - 12226.63)	10506.24 ± 1128.38 (8126.65 - 13033.17)	11208.36 ± 1241.76 (9085.04 - 13001.97)	10701.24 ± 1031.93 (8974.93 - 12672.22)	0.274	10969.97 ± 1156.69 (9613.10 - 13816.94)	10822.71 ± 1476.24 (8706.82 - 13159.07)	10361.22 ± 962.83 (9375.87 - 11840.68)	0.493

Left Crus I	17988.07 ± 2144.14 (6579.83 - 21373.06)	17384.04 ± 2295.39 (5667.15 - 20296.89)	17213.59 ± 1614.21 (14215.08 - 20637.10)	18767.59 ± 1778.24 (15881.17 - 20808.86)	17511.53 ± 1558.31 (15537.62 - 20684.86)	0.457	17763.73 ± 1689.76 (13774.84 - 20753.11)	18003.79 ± 2399.18 (15136.47 - 22365.30)	17581.07 ± 1553.18 (15693.68 - 19607.66)	0.702
Vermis Crus I	27.38 ± 5.92 (16.01 - 40.41)	27.63 ± 4.86 (15.37 - 37.62)	27.29 ± 5.92 (15.60 - 40.54)	28.89 ± 5.84 (20.89 -36.60)	32.28 ± 6.62 (21.92 - 42.93)	0.159	27.40 ± 6.37 (16.06 - 35.40)	31.15 ± 4.98 (24.13 - 41.28)	26.85 ± 2.23 (23.95 - 30.09)	0.214
Right Crus I	17517.67 ± 1713.27 (9367.11 - 19876.71)	17350.72 ± 2341.86 (6294.66 - 20112.91)	16957.10 ± 1554.86 (13918.91 - 20709.32)	18425.21 ± 1638.80 (15295.01 - 20590.42)	16911.63 ± 1543.43 (14894.19 - 19363.71)	0.329	17073.84 ± 2019.81 (13952.77 - 20454.22)	17157.07 ± 2074.49 (14122.34 - 20679.38)	16522.05 ± 1994.00 (13659.17 - 19668.27)	0.693
Left Crus II	13395.10 ± 1337.00 (9208.45 - 16246.67)	13146.82 ± 1305.75 (8863.41 - 15346.39)	12566.99 ± 997.33 (10887.73 - 14847.24)	13475.04 ± 1330.42 (11217.02 - 14996.43)	12871.95 ± 1096.92 (11450.44 - 14692.27)	0.193	13387.16 ± 1196.79 (11158.75 - 15290.59)	13488.13 ± 1810.46 (11698.63 - 17237.68)	12880.58 ± 1478.41 (10549.01 - 14908.25)	0.344
Vermis Crus II	543.66 ± 55.28 (391.92 - 638.49)	529.92 ± 45.00 (403.89 - 607.39)	505.41 ± 69.64 (376.50 - 656.91)	582.03 ± 54.34 (507.68 - 642.02)	531.05 ± 49.19 (461.22 - 595.19)	0.036	542.23 ± 47.17 (450.65 - 614.57)	544.87 ± 61.79 (474.61 - 645.49)	515.19 ± 60.19 (435.51 - 609.19)	0.425
Right Crus II	12608.73 ± 1116.27 (10445.79 - 14676.75)	12274.48 ± 1089.25 (10011.93 - 14671.86)	11593.72 ± 986.12 (10244.60 - 13671.81)	12322.57 ± 1379.74 (10131.02 - 14323.13)	11914.69 ± 744.48 (10756.49 - 13018.024)	0.033	12273.34 ± 1317.10 (10251.54 - 15300.30)	12395.29 ± 1457.97 (11045.84 - 15349.59)	11632.03 ± 1292.66 (9704.90 - 13495.74)	0.049
Left VIIIb	6777.29 ± 640.83 (5336.57 - 8326.35)	6579.04 ± 654.86 (5367.82 - 7808.39)	6206.21 ± 587.81 (5240.30 - 7521.90)	6775.47 ± 872.22 (5394.68 - 7874.31)	6470.08 ± 606.51 (5698.26 - 7752.60)	0.053	6787.21 ± 622.39 (5692.55 - 7935.25)	6745.29 ± 917.48 (5739.96 - 8710.29)	6471.64 ± 794.39 (5205.38 - 7635.49)	0.214
Vermis VIIIb	240.72 ± 36.27 (133.80 - 345.67)	220.32 ± 28.44 (117.39 - 263.82)	217.50 ± 35.79 (171.64 - 297.86)	250.21 ± 35.65 (197.73 - 298.22)	220.91 ± 36.34 (166.59 - 285.92)	0.093	236.14 ± 25.80 (196.04 -271.23)	233.96 ± 44.93 (192.28 - 321.98)	227.53 ± 29.39 (181.51 - 273.91)	0.356
Right VIIIb	6836.78 ± 608.77 (5483.39 - 8184.08)	6688.17 ± 617.31 (5269.94 - 7660.55)	6268.13 ± 664.35 (5075.89 - 7431.64)	6740.03 ± 819.71 (5433.13 - 7784.29)	6504.02 ± 465.88 (6025.50 - 7540.93)	0.027	6760.85 ± 626.77 (5778.92 - 7736.56)	6659.75 ± 824.34 (5875.21 - 8459.36)	6322.79 ± 687.47 (5325.27 - 7439.71)	0.058
Left VIIIa	7059.44 ± 699.10 (4501.80 - 8682.68)	6834.44 ± 667.90 (4976.7 ± 7938.36)	6524.07 ± 629.27 (5492.14 - 7978.23)	7207.63 ± 891.48 (5801.93 - 8418.51)	6780.92 ± 673.31 (5833.40 - 8247.12)	0.091	7200.25 ± 715.96 (6229.92 - 8751.78)	6998.64 ± 908.81 (6059.38 - 8847.86)	6860.01 ± 779.90 (5607.87 - 7826.47)	0.508
Vermis VIIIa	1547.16 ± 188.00 (792.14 - 1925.24)	1457.86 ± 174.96 (890.25 - 1800.19)	1445.03 ± 143.73 (1228.61 - 1752.10)	1677.29 ± 104.32 (1498.84 - 1804.51)	1479.34 ± 162.90 (1281.36 - 1788.95)	0.072	1506.94 ± 126.00 (1258.32 - 1693.58)	1554.55 ± 248.65 (1256.0 - 1998.03)	1478.84 ± 228.19 (1228.84 - 1783.48)	0.578
Right VIIIa	6483.28 ± 688.87	6370.20 ± 680.84	6060.24 ± 662.50	6453.89 ± 685.57	6166.26 ± 389.72	0.200	6563.34 ± 567.68 (5818.53 - 7589.59)	6399.01 ± 748.29 (5595.70 - 7939.34)	6206.72 ± 781.71 (5259.21 - 7612.67)	0.447

	(3506.01 - 7656.93)	(4092.09 - 7720.46)	(4962.37 - 7203.88)	(5149.08 - 7100.279)	(5535.06 - 7001.70)					
Left VIIIb	5661.24 ± 580.55 (3111.71 - 6628.33)	5484.83 ± 551.13 (3802.79 - 6482.95)	5317.10 ± 509.17 (4418.24 - 6257.43)	5949.81 ± 746.85 (4737.90 - 6946.41)	5453.24 ± 496.45 (4723.33 - 6299.16)	0.070	5821.86 ± 575.93 (4878.75 - 6705.25)	5701.20 ± 695.62 (4833.50 - 7263.62)	5453.76 ± 637.77 (4691.71 - 6405.55)	0.348
Vermis VIIIb	776.80 ± 81.73 (428.63 - 940.87)	756.36 ± 90.65 (470.98 - 950.25)	733.09 ± 90.56 (562.37 - 950.38)	853.03 ± 63.83 (762.04 - 934.82)	733.37 ± 81.07 (608.17 - 871.32)	0.057	783.22 ± 58.82 (673.25 - 866.99)	787.69 ± 124.57 (635.50 - 1031.05)	749.38 ± 113.33 (616.57 - 929.78)	0.593
Right VIIIb	5400.34 ± 502.96 (3105.79 - 6132.71)	5258.81 ± 499.73 (3352.77 - 6103.33)	5176.61 ± 469.49 (4194.79 - 6155.92)	5712.63 ± 744.30 (4243.55 - 6430.70)	5185.79 ± 463.06 (4458.14 - 5813.90)	0.167	5462.55 ± 498.92 (4510.07 - 6144.61)	5360.07 ± 563.61 (4619.55 - 6498.71)	5140.91 ± 655.65 (4434.56 - 6271.02)	0.372
Left IX	4369.81 ± 486.42 (2600.20 - 5269.52)	4283.77 ± 448.41 (3284.17 - 5259.15)	4198.38 ± 399.02 (3667.94 - 5085.29)	4746.25 ± 501.93 (3935.96 - 5293.86)	4143.08 ± 417.18 (3435.61 - 4812.93)	0.108	4359.53 ± 435.15 (3615.10 - 5052.50)	4336.01 ± 642.13 (3289.08 - 5390.65)	4138.39 ± 586.46 (3561.14 - 5062.83)	0.426
Vermis IX	915.68 ± 115.59 (504.41 - 1202.48)	878.48 ± 107.19 (651.55 - 1136.24)	863.76 ± 103.58 (709.83 - 1080.14)	993.72 ± 111.80 (796.45 - 1097.06)	873.24 ± 105.98 (719.08 - 1053.17)	0.148	923.62 ± 98.88 (770.64 - 1076.22)	907.20 ± 159.22 (737.62 - 1178.14)	889.50 ± 122.64 (762.15 - 1078.91)	0.665
Right IX	4571.85 ± 525.48 (2627.43 - 5465.87)	4431.04 ± 432.24 (3595.61 - 5367.82)	4357.80 ± 388.46 (3884.43 - 5071.77)	5007.34 ± 505.67 (4089.76 - 5598.73)	4350.30 ± 446.97 (3509.56 - 5041.07)	0.058	4526.81 ± 467.62 (3763.81 - 5440.52)	4543.05 ± 600.48 (3849.01 - 5591.70)	4360.07 ± 656.05 (3637.77 - 5292.62)	0.511
Left X	918.90 ± 100.54 (472.44 - 1122.37)	914.79 ± 98.05 (725.94 - 1100.64)	883.89 ± 81.70 (752.37 - 1038.02)	961.86 ± 88.90 (849.81 - 1069.83)	934.04 ± 97.24 (763.28 - 1059.28)	0.426	925.49 ± 109.02 (771.38 - 1166.27)	916.73 ± 114.42 (750.57 - 1179.11)	930.81 ± 111.39 (788.03 - 1097.82)	0.991
Vermis X	489.09 ± 68.21 (320.88 - 655.32)	507.85 ± 85.13 (338.21 - 709.38)	494.47 ± 67.94 (369.30 - 627.86)	523.56 ± 80.00 (389.20 - 640.14)	528.70 ± 66.96 (436.70 - 679.55)	0.483	544.71 ± 85.73 (391.78 - 714.88)	573.39 ± 120.85 (460.83 - 870.97)	533.98 ± 104.87 (409.82 - 698.33)	0.051
Right X	902.45 ± 103.20 (468.89 - 1140.85)	901.31 ± 120.72 (422.06 - 1104.77)	897.81 ± 82.83 (785.87 - 1089.17)	965.98 ± 115.50 (776.83 - 1102.65)	898.39 ± 105.80 (734.38 - 1084.31)	0.825	909.77 ± 101.10 (714.02 - 1069.86)	922.59 ± 88.41 (801.87 - 1114.10)	923.71 ± 98.46 (795.22 - 1086.52)	0.693

Values (mm³) are reported as mean ± SD [max. value – min. value]. P values refer to age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons are reported in **eTable 11**. Abbreviations: HC= healthy controls; sMND= sporadic motor neuron disease; sFTD= sporadic frontotemporal dementia; C9-MND= motor neuron disease with *C9orf72* mutation; C9-FTD= frontotemporal dementia with *C9orf72* mutation; SOD1= motor neuron disease due to *SOD1* mutation; TARDBP= motor neuron disease due to *TARDBP* mutation; GRN= frontotemporal dementia due to *GRN* mutation.

Values (mm^3) are referred to age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. Abbreviations: HC= healthy controls; sMND= sporadic motor neuron disease; sFTD= sporadic frontotemporal dementia; C9-MND= motor neuron disease with *C9orf72* mutation; C9-FTD= frontotemporal dementia with *C9orf72* mutation; SOD1= motor neuron disease due to *SOD1* mutation; TARDBP= motor neuron disease due to *TARDBP* mutation; GRN= frontotemporal dementia due to *GRN* mutation.

Level 1 – HC vs sFTLD vs gFTLD

eFigure 1. Box-plots reporting GM volumes of selected subcortical and cerebellar structures in gFTLD and sFTLD patients. Comparisons between groups were made using age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. *Symbols: * = $p < 0.05$ compared with HC; # = $p < 0.05$ compared with sFTLD.* Abbreviations: FTL D= frontotemporal lobar degeneration; GM= grey matter; g= genetic; HC= healthy controls; s= sporadic.

Level 3 – HC vs sMND vs C9-MND vs SOD1 vs TARDBP / HC vs sFTD vs C9-FTD vs GRN

eFigure 2. Box-plots reporting GM volumes of selected subcortical and cerebellar structures in FTLN patients according to genetic mutation. Comparisons between groups were made using age-, sex- and MR scanner-adjusted ANOVA models, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons, Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons. *Symbols:* * = $p < 0.05$ compared with HC; # = $p < 0.05$ compared with sMND. *Abbreviations:* C9-FTD= frontotemporal dementia patients carrying a C9orf72 mutation; C9-MND= motor neuron disease patients carrying a C9orf72 mutation; FTD= frontotemporal dementia; GM= grey matter; HC= healthy controls; MND= motor neuron disease; s= sporadic.